

Relativistic Correction to the Harmonic Oscillator in 1D

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In recent notes (1) (2), a method is developed for obtaining relativistic corrections to the nonrelativistic energy given an appropriate relativistic equation. The relativistic DE does not need to be solved. In (3), a Klein-Gordon equation is proposed for the harmonic oscillator. This equation is solved exactly and energy values obtained. In this note, we assume that one does not have the relativistic energy expression and determine corrections to the Schrodinger energy using the method of (1) and (2). We then compare the results to the exact relativistic expression expanded in powers of m . We consider two orders of corrections beyond the Schrodinger energy.

Klein-Gordon Equation for the Oscillator

The authors of (3) begin with the free Klein-Gordon equation in 1D:

$$[p^*p - (E^*E - m^*m)] W = 0 \quad ((1))$$

They then replace p with $p - imw$ and define $p^t = p + imw$ and $p^*p = .5(p^t + p^t p)$ where $w = \sqrt{k/m}$. Here \hbar and c are set to 1. The result is:

$$[d/dx \ d/dx - m^*m \ w^*w + (E^*E - m^*m)] W(x) = 0 \quad ((2))$$

They then set $f = mw$ and transform using $y = f x^*x$ to obtain:

$$y \ d/dy \ d/dy \ W + \frac{1}{2} \ d/dy \ W + (k'/2 - \frac{1}{4} y) W = 0 \quad ((3))$$

With $k' = (E^*E - m^*m) / (2mw)$. They solve ((3)) exactly and obtain:

$$E^*E = m^*m + 2(n+.5) mw \quad ((4))$$

$$\text{Thus: } E = e + m = m(1 + (n+.5) m^{-3/2} \sqrt{k} - (n+.5)^2 m^{-3} k + \dots)$$

The first order correction is: $e = (n+.5) w$ which is the nonrelativistic result.

$$\text{The second order correction is: } -1/2(n+.5)(n+.5) w^*w/m \quad ((3a))$$

$$\text{The third order correction is: } \frac{1}{2} (n+.5)^3 w^3/m^2 \quad ((3b))$$

Method of (1) (2) for Finding Relativistic Corrections

The approach of (1) and (2) is to note that in the relativistic case:

$$\text{Prel } W(x) = \hbar/i \, d/dx \, W(x)$$

In the nonrelativistic case, one replaces the above with: $p (W_0 + W_1 + W_2 \dots)$ where $p = \hbar/i$, W_0 equals the Schrodinger wavefunction and W_1, W_2 etc are corrections. In other words, there is no correction to d/dx derivatives. Any power (d/dx) derivative in the relativistic case becomes the same d/dx power derivative in the nonrelativistic one. The relativistic wavefunction, however, is still the relativistic function and needs to be written as the Schrodinger wavefunction plus corrections. (See (2) for details. A Fourier series argument is used.)

One may then examine the relativistic equation and attempt to expand it in terms of various powers of m noting that $E = e + m$ and $e^*e + 2me$ where $e^*e \ll 2me$ for the nonrelativistic case. Furthermore, $e = e_0 + g$ where g is a correction and e_0 the Schrodinger energy. (See (1) and (2).) This strategy is applied to ((3)). We deal with the ground state energy.

In ((3)), $k' = (E^*E - m^*m) / (2mw)$. For the nonrelativistic approximation, we use:

$$k' = 2me / 2mw = (e_0 + g)/w. \text{ The first approximation is to set } g = 0.$$

e_0 is the Schrodinger ground state energy so: $e_0 = .5 w$. $f = mw$

Finally, W_0 , the Schrodinger ground state is $\exp(-a x^2)$ where $a = \sqrt{km}/2$.

Thus, the terms of ((3)) represent different powers of m and one can break ((3)) into two equations, namely:

$$y \, d/dy \, d/dy \, W - \frac{1}{4} y \, W = 0 \quad ((4)) \quad \text{and} \quad .5 \, d/dy \, W + k'/2 \, W = 0 \quad ((5))$$

The first equation represents a power of $1/\sqrt{m}$ while the second a constant in terms of m .

The next step is to obtain a correction to the Schrodinger energy. We use ((5)) and note:

$$k' = [e^*e + 2me] / 2mw \quad \text{The next correction is: } e_0^*e_0/2mw + 2me_0/2mw + 2mg/2mw = e_0^*e_0/2mw + e_0/w + g/w$$

Thus, the $k'/2 \, W$ term is: $.5(e_0^*e_0/2mw + e_0/w + g/w) \, W$ but $W = W_0 + W_1$ where W_0 is the Schrodinger result and W_1 a correction. Thus, the $k'/2 \, W$ terms becomes in the correction:

$$e_0^*e_0/4mw + 2mg/4mw + .5e_0/w \, W_1 \quad ((6)) \quad \text{This gives an order of } m^{-3/2} \text{ imposed by the first term}$$

((5)) then becomes:

$$\frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dy} W_1 + \frac{e_0^* e_0}{4mw} + \frac{2mg}{4mw} + .5 \frac{e_0}{w} W_1 = 0 \quad ((7))$$

W_0 is of the form $\exp(-ay)$ and $\exp(ky)$ form a basis. Thus, the terms with W_1 should cancel with each other and those with W_0 should do the same so:

$$\frac{e_0^* e_0}{4mw} + \frac{2mg}{4mw} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad g = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{w^* w}{m} (n+.5)^2 \quad ((8))$$

This is the relativistic correction given by ((3a)) so the results match for the ground state.

The same argument holds for higher energy levels because ((8)) is independent of energy levels and must always hold.

Next Order Relativistic Correction

From ((3b)) the third order correction (Schrodinger e_0 is first order) is $.5 \frac{w^3}{m^2}$.

To obtain this, consider:

$$k'/2 = \frac{(e^* e + 2em)}{2m} = \frac{(e_0 + g + g^2)(e_0 + g + g^2) + 2(e_0 + g + g^2)m}{2m}$$

The relevant terms are:

$\frac{2e_0 g}{2m} + \frac{2m g^2}{2m} = 0$ Again, the W piece used with $k'/2$ is W_0 and we consider the coefficient of this as 0.

Thus, $g^2 = \frac{1}{2} (n+.5)^3 \frac{w^3}{m^2}$ which is the same as ((3b))

Conclusion

In conclusion, we apply the method of (1), (2) to obtain a relativistic correction to the nonrelativistic harmonic oscillator. This method requires a starting relativistic equation. We use that of (3) and compare the results with the exact relativistic solution (obtained in (3)). The two agree.

References

1. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Corrections to the 1-D Schrodinger Equation Using Fourier Series (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
2. Ruggeri, Francesco R. Relativistic Corrections to the 1D Schrodinger Equation for the Infinite Potential Well (preprint, zenodo, 2019)
3. Rao, N. and Kagali, B. On the Energy Spectrum of the One Dimensional Klein-Gordon Oscillator <https://arxiv.org/pdf/0704.1869.pdf>